

The Impact of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) on Firms' Financial Stability: Evidence from Egypt

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to empirically investigate the effect of the Financial Regulatory Authority (FRA)'s decree no. 108/2021 to measure the impact of the overall and the individual Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) factors on the firm stability in Egypt; as it is an emerging country. The study sample covers 106 firms listed in the Egyptian Stock Exchange (EGX) during the period 2020 to 2023. Panel regression analysis was used to examine the study hypotheses and achieve the study aims. The results showed that ESG disclosure negatively affects a firm's stability measured by Z-score. However, measuring ESG subcomponents separately showed that environmental (E), social (S) and governance (G) disclosure are negatively associated with Z-score. More importantly, ESG, E, S and G tend to be higher with firms that have high assets and high block-holders; but ESG, E, S and G tend to be lower with old firms. Furthermore, after the FRA's decree application, the higher level of ESG, E, S and G

disclosure. The study limns a vision of the FRA's decree no. 108/2021 application on the impact of ESG disclosure on firm stability in Egypt. This study tries to determine whether there are relationships among all ESG disclosure and FS, and if they are positive, negative or even neutral.

Keywords: ESG disclosure, Financial Stability, EGX, Corporate governance, Blockholders.

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1. Introduction

Recently, there is a growing demand for improving business reporting, with more focus by the firms on providing more non-financial information, such as: customer satisfaction, employee engagement, social impact, environmental footprint and innovation can provide additional insights and context to the financial analysis. Non-financial reporting standards require firms to formally disclose data regularly covering Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) topics including Greenhouse Gases (GHG) emissions, energy and carbon credits but also other environmental themes like water or biodiversity.

Sustainable development is not only related to corporate social responsibility (CSR) and accounting standards but also associated with customer satisfaction. Environmental, social and governance disclosures (ESGDs) offer a more significant opportunity to understand firms' nonfinancial reporting. Non-financial information can help corporate managers in the fulfilment of their strategic environmental objectives [1].

The United Nations (UN) has introduced the initiative of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), in 2015 as a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet and ensure that by 2030 all people enjoy peace and prosperity, that is comprised of 17 main goals that relate to the human rights as well as the environmental issues and corporate reporting.

In compliance with the UN SDGs, Egypt launched "Egypt Vision 2030" which consists of 8 main national goals that are in line with the 17 UN SDGs. Further to this, by 2030, all firms are expected to disclose information related to their environmental and social effect.

Nowadays, there are many different definitions and terms for responsible investing and ESG principles. In the framework of this research, the study uses a definition of ESG principles based on the European Commission's vision and on the UN Principles [2]. Environmentalism stands for the principles of green finance, understood as the process of decision making in the investment phase. Social considerations may refer to issues of inequality, inclusiveness, labor relations, investment in human capital and communities. The governance of public and private institutions, including management structures, employee relations and executive remuneration, plays a fundamental role in ensuring the inclusion of social and environmental considerations in the decision-making process. The integration of the three components constitutes a set of sustainable development principles both in economic and financial terms.

The interpretation of ESG used in the framework of this research was selected for two main reasons. First, the subject of study is Egyptian companies. Egyptian legislation on the subject has been developed according to Egypt's vision 2030 standards and principles. The second is the fact that the ESG ratings of Egyptian companies were developed by the Financial Regulatory Authority (FRA)'s decree no 108/2021, which follows UN SDGs.

ESG Disclosure Reports: are reports that disclose data explaining the impact of businesses and their added value in the three pillars: environment, society and governance, like the financial reports issued by companies periodically. These reports provide a summary of quantitative and qualitative disclosures supported by a performance analysis of environmental, social and governance factors, which is an internal perspective (Sustainable Development Department at Financial Regulatory Association, 2021).

Recently, asset managers, pension funds and institutional investors assess ESG activities of companies when determining investment decisions. In both academic and professional environments, prior literature has proven that ESG disclosure would enhance the firm's credibility [3-6]. ESG facilitates to investors, decisionmakers, regulators, policymakers, scholars and stakeholders to improve their awareness and knowledge about ESG disclosure practices in relation to current and future performance. ESG is a commonly researched concept, which has been considered as an important part of the strategy of the firm because it might have a crucial effect on firm performance (FP) [1]. The importance of this topic has also been stressed by the dissemination of the SDGs by the UN, which highlighted the importance of environmental and social issues towards sustainable growth for both firms and countries.

In Egypt, the ESG disclosure was not obligatory, some Egyptian companies voluntarily disclose ESG information via their annual reports and/or Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) reports, moreover, in 2021, Egypt has started working toward making sustainability obligatory through the initiative of the Board of Directors of the Financial Regulatory Authority (FRA) who issued decree no. 108 of 2021 dated 05/07/2021, which obligates listed companies on the Egyptian Stock Exchange (EGX) to undertake annual ESG reporting starting from year 2022. The ESG pillars will be discussed in detail in the methodology section. The decree is applied in two stages: The first stage: the compliance or explain stage. The second stage: the stage of exposure to legal accountability and the application of fines or penalties on non-compliant companies.

As ESG ratings is becoming a global trend all over the world, the relationship between ESG, Financial Stability (FS) needs to be further investigated in the context of Egypt, which is an emerging market. Due to the importance of ESG and its impact on company's reputation and image, the research aims to explore the ESG reporting by the Egyptian firms and to test the impact of ESG disclosure on the financial stability of the firms, taking into consideration the FRA's decree No. 108/2021.

The study is relevant to both practitioners and academics as the findings of this study have practical implications for firms' managers and board of directors in adopting and disclosing ESG initiatives to increase firm value in providing them with a deeper knowledge on the influence of ESG on firm stability which further assists with selecting the best choices for their strategic goals. Further, regulators of Corporate Governance (CG) codes can use this study's results as empirical support for developing new regulations and amendments and implementing necessary corrective decisions regarding the effectiveness of applying CG codes.

To the best of author's knowledge this is considered the first empirical study which uses data to determine the impact of ESG practices on firm stability through the FRA's decree no 108/2021. To the knowledge of the authors, no previous paper has investigated the impact of the FRA's decree of ESG factors on company stability in Egypt.

Therefore, academics can utilize the findings of the current study in exploring avenues related to ESG in various other countries which are not fully developed yet. Further, this study adds to literature review by using recent sample data of EGX firms as well as considering the three individual dimensions of ESG in the analysis and further revealing the moderating role of firm block-holders in the relationship between ESG and corporate financial stability. As FS is of interest because in many cases are slower to carry out ESG activities because they are

perceived as having scarcity of resources and do not see these activities as a priority; they justify not investing in ESG because they do not have liquid resources and are conditioned by ESG practices' commitment to their level of liquidity.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 offers an overview of the relevant literature. Section 3 describes the data and methodology to be used in this study. Section 4 presents the results. Section 5 presents the analysis and discussion. Section 6 concludes the research.

2. Literature review

2.1. Theoretical Framework

This study empirically examines two main contrasting theories explaining the impact of ESG on financial stability. They are the shareholder and stakeholder value maximization theories. While shareholder-focused theory believes that ESG engagement is detrimental to firm value, the stakeholder-focused theory advocates the benefits of ESG practice which could enhance firm value [7,8]. From a long-term perspective, fulfilling ESG can help promote the relationship between the management and various stakeholders, thus improve firm stability. Specifically, by satisfying the various stakeholders' needs, a firm can establish a reputation and establish competitive advantages [9,10]. Therefore, the promotion effect based on the stakeholder theory may need to be manifested in the long term. This research confirms the second one in the context of the Egyptian market.

Among the important theories that guide the firms in such context are the agency theory and the trade-off theory. The Agency theory [11] is the relationship between principal and agent. At this point, a conflict of interest arises between the principal – having a long-time horizon orientation – and the agent – having a short-time horizon orientation –. Thus, the higher the level of non-financial information disclosure, in other words, ESG, the happier the principal will be, because of the higher transparency. As for the trade-off theory, fulfilling ESG responsibility can negatively impact financial stability in the short run. Hence, whenever a company gets more involved in ESG, the corresponding costs tend to rise, and profits tend to fall, thus generating a loss in terms of shareholder value. This is called the substitution effect [12]. This negative impact will gradually weaken.

So, both trade-off and stakeholder's theories are aligned, one for the short-term and the other for the long-term.

2.2. Empirical Background

2.2.1 The impact of ESG, E, S and G factors on financial stability

Recent studies have established a positive correlation between sustainability and firm stability.

[13] examined 15 representative financial firms listed on the Korea Composite Stock Price Index (KOSPI) in the period from 2013 to 2022, measuring financial stability using Altman's Z-score and found that the ESG score is aggregated and the ESG coefficient shows positive statistical significance. Also, they found that all E, S and G pillars have a positive and significant impact with financial stability, meanwhile, it seems the E pillar plays the most significant role in enhancing financial stability in the finance industry. Also, the results for non-bank financial intermediaries (NBFIs) are similar.

This research only studied the financial firms in Korea, neglecting all other sectors.

[14] examined ESG score in European banking and found that higher overall ESG score contributes to greater bank stability during periods of financial risk. They argued that a greater commitment to ESG practices in the banking sector has positive effects on both the environment and society. Likewise, they found that higher all E, S and G pillars' scores contribute to greater bank stability during periods of financial risk. They argued that a greater commitment to E, S and G practices in the banking sector has positive effects on the environment and society and corporate governance.

To conclude, based on the previous studies which report positive findings this study aims to contribute to the literature on the impact of ESG, E, S and G disclosure on firm stability in the context of the Egyptian market. Hence, the following main hypothesis and sub-hypotheses are proposed:

H1: ESG score has an impact on firm financial stability (FS).

H1.1: E score has an impact on firm financial stability (FS).

H1.2: S score has an impact on firm financial stability (FS).

H1.3: G score has an impact on firm financial stability (FS).

3. Materials and Methods

This section presents the data and the sample of the study, followed by the research model and a description of variables. The study uses a panel data model for the dependent variable and four models in total for each independent variable.

3.1. Data and sample

The study sample comprises annual data for all firms listed in the Egyptian Stock Exchange (EGX) for the companies that have ending-year by December, excluding 2 sectors: Banks and Non-Banking Financial Services sectors; as they have a specific nature, during the period 2020 to 2023; two years before the application of the FRA's decree no. 108/2021 and two years after its application. The study selects this period as it is the most recent four consecutive year-period at the time of writing the article. This selection resulted in 424 observations derived from 106 listed firms after excluding 154 firms due to irrelevant or missing data from a total number of 260 firms listed in EGX. All the data used in this study is secondary data; as the study gets the ESG score from the annual ESG report, also, the study gets the data for the financial performance variables and the firm size, as a control variable, from the annual financial statements. The data for the block-holders and firm age, as control variables, is collected from the annual corporate governance disclosure report available on the firms' respective online platforms or specialized websites or data available at the Egyptian Company for Information Dissemination (EGID). As for the Market price, this study uses the end of year price (market value at 31th December) of each of the four years. As for the methodology used, this study uses a regression model using SPSS program.

3.2. Research Model

This section presents the research model, where the ESG, E, S and G scores are the independent variables to measure their effect on the firms' Financial Stability, measured Z-score, as dependent variables, by the control effect of the Firm Size, Firm Age and Block-holders.

To measure ESG impact on FS, the study estimates a linear regression model as one main model and three sub-models as follows:

$$FS = \beta_0 + \beta_1E + \beta_2S + \beta_3G + \beta_4Size + \beta_5Age + \beta_6Block + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

$$FS = \beta_0 + \beta_1E + \beta_2S + \beta_3G + \beta_4Size + \beta_5Age + \beta_6Block + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

$$FS = \beta_0 + \beta_1E + \beta_2S + \beta_3G + \beta_4Size + \beta_5Age + \beta_6Block + \epsilon \quad (3)$$

$$FS = \beta_0 + \beta_1E + \beta_2S + \beta_3G + \beta_4Size + \beta_5Age + \beta_6Block + \epsilon \quad (4)$$

3.3. Variables measurement

Given that an ESG score is a multidimensional index built on the outputs of environmental, social and governance disclosure and the impact of one dimension may sometimes eliminate opposing effects of another dimension, it is useful to have separate data available. ESG report is a questionnaire that will be transformed to an index to obtain the overall ESG, E, S and G scores. The study's explanatory variables of interest are the scores for overall ESG (ESG) and individual ESG pillars (E, S and G). The FRA's decree no. 108/2021 evaluates companies according to 3 pillars: environmental, social and governance based on 17 indicators (5 environmental, 6 social and 6 governance ones). ESG score has value range from 0 to 41, with 41 as the highest score.

E score: contains 5 indicators: (E1) Environmental Operations & Oversight, (E2) Carbon emissions / Greenhouse gases, (E3) Energy sources usage and diversification, (E4) Water usage and (E5) Waste management. E score has value range from 0 to 13, with 13 as the highest score.

S score: contains 6 indicators: (S1) Gender diversity & pay ratio, (S2) Employee turnover rate, (S3) Non-discrimination, (S4) Global health & safety standards, (S5) Children & Forced Labor and (S6) Labor rights. S score has value range from 0 to 16, with 16 as the highest score.

G score: contains 6 indicators: (G1) Board diversity, (G2) Bribery / Anti-corruption, (G3) Ethics and code of conduct, (G4) Data privacy, (G5) Sustainability reporting & disclosure and (G6) External Assurance. G score has value range from 0 to 12, with 12 as the highest score.

The report of the companies under study is completed by the Investor Relations (IR) manager or the Compliance Officer or the Chief Financial Officer or the Human Resources manager.

As the ESG disclosure has impact on the firm's stability, the study measures Financial Stability (FS) using Z-score – a measure to predict how likely a company will become insolvent – typically, a lower Z score value indicates a higher risk of bankruptcy and vice visa [15]. A higher Z-score level indicates a lower likelihood of bankruptcy, whereas a lower score suggests a greater risk of financial difficulty –. Altman, considers several financial ratios and variables, such as profitability, liquidity, leverage, solvency and activity, the study calculates the Z-score value of each financial firm by using five factors; where Z-score: $\zeta = 1.2A + 1.4B + 3.3C + 0.6D + 1.0E$, where: A: Cash (C) / Total Assets (TA) – a liquidity ratio –, B: Retained Earnings

(RE) / Total Assets (TA) – a leverage ratio –, C: Earnings Before Interest and Tax (EBIT) / Total Assets (TA) – a profitability ratio –, D: Total Equity (TE) / Total Liabilities (TL) – a solvency ratio – and E: Sales (S) / Total Assets (TA) – an activity ratio –. The Z-score level serves as a predictive tool to assess the firm’s financial soundness and default probability [16]. The choice of the firms’ stability variable as dependent variable in this study follows [13,15].

The study evaluates the control variables based on three dimensions: using the firm size (FS), where FS = Natural log of Total Assets (Ln TA), using firm age (FA), where FA = Natural log of Age (date of registration on the EGX) (Ln age) and using block-holders (BH), where BH = Sum of shareholders having 5% or more shares. The choice of firm size as control variables in this study follows [17-22]. This study follows [22,23] in employing firm age as control variable. Likewise, the year in which the firm has been registered in Egyptian Stock Exchange (EGX) is used as the base year for calculating the firm’s age. This study follows [1, 24, 25] in employing block-holders as control variable.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive analysis

In this section, the mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum and median of the variables used in this study are presented. In addition, skewness to assess the lack of symmetry and kurtosis tests are presented to assess whether the data are normally distributed. As shown in Table 1, the data is normally distributed; Skewness is around (0) for all study independent variables and kurtosis is around (0) for all variables except for the E score variable (-1.29).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the study variables.

Variable	Descriptive statistics					Normality tests	
	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Median	Skew-Kurtoness	sis
Independent variables:							
E score	6.87	4.39	0	13	7.00	-0.19	-1.29
S score	8.63	4.37	0	16	9.00	-0.34	-0.84
G score	6.68	3.30	0	12	7.00	-0.40	-0.67
ESG score	22.18	10.44	0	41	23.00	-0.42	-0.58

Dependent variables:

Z-score	2.31	3.69	-8.63	53.11	1.79	7.65	92.69
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Control variables:

FS	20.92	1.98	16.55	26.03	21.04	0.28	-0.45
FA	2.82	0.65	0.00	3.85	3.09	-1.40	2.40
BH	0.61	0.21	0.00	0.9616		0.63	-0.585 -0.15

The table shows descriptive statistics for the independent variables: ESG score, E score, S score and G score, the dependent variable: Z-score and the control variables: FS, FA and BH used in the study from 2020 to 2023. The sample analysis includes 424 observations. The E score serves as an indicator of the environmental initiatives and activities, S score serves as an indicator of the social initiatives and activities and the G score serves as an indicator of the governance initiatives and activities. Z-score serves as an indicator of the financial stability. Firm Size, Firm Age and Block-holders are FS, FA and BH respectively as the control variables.

4.2. Correlation analysis

In this section, the correlation outputs, with a focus on testing the relationships between the study variables (dependent and independent variables) are presented.

Table 2. Correlation results for ESG score.

	Zscore	MeanESG	FS	FA	BH	
Pearson Correlation Zscore	1.000					
	MeanESG	-0.174***	1.000			
	FS	-0.215***	0.381***	1.000		
	FA	-0.044	-0.060	-0.054	1.000	
	BH	-0.134***	0.161***	0.399***	0.133***	1.000

* Significance at: *10%; **5% and ***1% levels.

4.3. Regression analysis

After conducting the descriptive analysis of the variables and testing the correlation analysis, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is used to check the multicollinearity. If the value of VIF is more than five, than it is suggested that there is a problem of multicollinearity. The results of VIF of all the models given in Table 3.

Table 3. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF).

Model	VIF
(Constant)	
MeanESG	1.174
MeanE	1.154
E1	1.730
E2	1.406
E3	2.526
E4	2.027
E5	1.923
MeanS	1.079
S1	1.671
S2	1.686
S3	3.162
S4	1.322
S5	3.276
S6	1.287
MeanG	1.100
G1	1.260
G2	1.765
G3	1.938
G4	1.486
G5	1.377
G6	1.081

In this section, the study applies regression analysis to test the impact of ESG and its subcomponents [E, S and G (independent variables)] on firms' stability [Z-score (dependent variable)].

As shown in Table 4, the results show that the ESG score has a significant negative relationship with Z-score.

Table 4. Regression results for ESG score.

Model Variables	Z-score		
	B	Std. Error	t
(Constant)	10.384***	2.113	4.916
MeanESG	-0.823**	0.389	-2.114
FS	-0.293***	0.101	-2.917
FA	-0.293	0.271	-1.078
BH	-1.001	0.899	-1.114
Adjusted R Square	0.054		

* Significance at: *10%; **5% and ***1% levels.

As for the ESG sub-components (E, S and G scores), the regression results are showed in Tables 5, 6 and 7. As for the E score sub-components, S score sub-components and G score sub-components, the regression results are showed in Tables 5.1, 6.1 and 7.1.

Table 5. Regression results for E score.

Model Variables	Z-score		
	B	Std. Error	t
(Constant)	10.986***	2.066	5.317
MeanE	-0.827**	0.378	-2.189
FS	-0.316***	0.097	-3.254
FA	-0.386	0.277	-1.396
BH	-0.838	0.905	-0.926
Adjusted R Square	0.054		

* Significance at: *10%; **5% and ***1% levels.

Table 5.1. Regression results for E score sub-components.

Model		Z-score		
Variables	B	Std. Error	t	
(Constant)	11.343***	2.133	5.317	
E1	-1.248***	0.472	-2.642	
E2	0.344	0.473	0.727	
E3	0.625	0.572	1.093	
E4	-0.953*	0.55	-1.734	
E5	0.293	0.481	0.609	
FS	-0.329***	0.102	-3.24	
FA	-0.309	0.279	-1.105	
BH	-0.712	0.917	-0.776	
Adjusted R Square	0.061			

² Significance at: *10%; **5% and ***1% levels.

Table 6. Regression results for S score.

Model		Z-score		
Variables	B	Std. Error	t	
(Constant)	11.124***	2.079	5.349	
MeanS	-0.426	0.375	-1.137	
FS	-0.339***	0.098	-3.472	
FA	-0.282	0.273	-1.035	
BH	-1.087	0.901	-1.205	

² Significance at: *10%; **5% and ***1% levels.

Table 6.1. Regression results for S score sub-components.

Adjusted R Square 0.047

Model Variables	Z-score		
	B	Std. Error	t
(Constant)	11.362***	2.157	5.269
S1	-0.132	0.46	-0.288
S2	-0.16	0.466	-0.343
S3	-1.119	0.864	-1.295
S4	-0.005	0.409	-0.013
S5	1.024	0.81	1.264
S6	-0.579	0.4	-1.449
FS	-0.331***	0.101	-3.273
FA	-0.301	0.275	-1.096
BH	-1.151	0.912	-1.262
Adjusted R Square	0.044		

² Significance at: *10%; **5% and ***1% levels.

Table 7. Regression results for G score.

Model Variables	Z-score		
	B	Std. Error	t
(Constant)	10.844***	2.072	5.234
MeanG	-0.869**	0.387	-2.248
FS	-0.307***	0.098	-3.138
FA	-0.313	0.272	-1.15
BH	-1.076	0.897	-1.199
Adjusted R Square	0.055		

³ Significance at: *10%; **5% and ***1% levels.

Table 7.1. Regression results for G score sub-components.

Model Variables	Z-score		
	B	Std. Error	t
(Constant)	10.191***	2.148	4.744
G1	0.097	0.598	0.162
G2	-0.043	0.558	-0.077
G3	0.348	0.529	0.657
G4	-0.850**	0.427	-1.988
G5	-0.856**	0.41	-2.087
G6	1.061**	0.536	1.98
FS	-0.271***	0.101	-2.686
FA	-0.321	0.273	-1.176
BH	-1.262	0.9	-1.403
Adjusted R Square	0.064		

* Significance at: *10%; **5% and ***1% levels.

5. Discussion

5.1. Descriptive analysis

Table 1 shows that the mean of total ESG disclosure of Egyptian companies is 22.18. The mean of S disclosure has the highest value (8.63) followed by E disclosure (6.87), while G disclosure has the lowest disclosure among the companies (6.68). This indicates that Egyptian companies positively practiced S disclosure and sought to increase this level of disclosure due to its impact on companies. For the E and G disclosures, the means are slightly weak, so there is still a gap to be filled to gain the benefits of E and G disclosures.

As for the minimum and the maximum; the results show that some companies get the minimum value of score for the whole period of the study, ESG, E, S and G scores = 0. While other companies are found to be the most compliant to the ESG disclosure; as they get the maximum values of score for the whole period of the study, E score = 13, S score = 16 and G

score = 1. So, from the study's sample some companies got the maximum ESG score = 41 only for the post-decree period.

As for the stability measure, the mean average of Z-score has a positive value (mean = 2.31).

As for the control variables, the mean average of firm size (FS) has a positive value (mean = 20.92), the mean average of firm age (FA) has a positive value (mean = 2.82) with a maximum of 3.85 for 47 years registered in EGX and the mean average of block-holders (BH) has a positive value (mean = 0.61) with a minimum of 0% and a maximum of 96.16%.

5.2. Correlation analysis

In Table 2, the results show that there is a negative relationship between ESG score and Zscore. This indicates that firms with high level of ESG have a lower financial stability.

As for the ESG sub-components (E, S and G) separately, this research checks for the multicollinearity problems and as all values are below 0.7, therefore no multicollinearity problems are presented in this study.

In terms of the control variables, FS variable is negatively correlated to the financial stability variable. Also, FA variable is negatively correlated to the financial stability. Moreover, BH variable is negatively correlated to the financial stability variable.

5.3. Regression analysis

The results of VIF of all the models given in Table 3 conclude that the values of VIF for all the variables is less than 5, which is an evidence that there is no significant multicollinearity and confirms the reliability of the regression analysis in the explanatory variables of the study.

First, in Table 5, regression analysis shows that E disclosure is negatively associated with Zscore. As for the 5 categories of the E pillar, the results show in Table 5.1: E1 negatively significant related, while E2 is positively insignificant associated. E3 is positively insignificant associated. E4 is negatively significant related. E5 is positively insignificant associated.

Second, in Table 6, the results indicate an insignificant negative relationship between S disclosure and firm's financial stability (Z-score) for EGX listed firms. This may be due to the cost of practicing and publishing S disclosure. As for the 6 categories of the S pillar, the results show in Table 6.1: S1 is negatively insignificant affecting Z-score. S2 is negatively insignificant affecting Z-score. S3 is negatively insignificant affecting Z-score. S4 is negatively insignificant affecting Z-score. S5 is positively insignificant affecting Z-score. S6 is negatively insignificant affecting Z-score.

Third, in Table 7, G disclosure was found to negatively significant affecting Z-score. As for the 6 categories of the G pillar, the results show in Table 7.1: G1 is positively insignificant associated, while G2 is negatively associated. G3 is positively insignificant associated, per contra, G4 is negatively significant associated. G5 is negatively significant associated, while G6 is positively significant associated.

Finally, when it comes to control variables, the results are the same for all the three of them. As for firm size, the results showed that firm size was found to be negatively insignificant affecting Z-score. Regarding the age as a control variable, the results showed that firm age is negatively insignificant. As for the shareholders' concentration, the results revealed that the block-holders are negatively insignificant affecting Z-score.

Notably, the impact of ESG on firm financial stability is mainly driven by the governance factor. This means that effective corporate governance practice can create negative results in the context of corporate financial stability.

Although these results do not follow previous literature [13,14] as previous literature were covering a period of 10 years or more, while the Egyptian decree no. 108/2021 is only applied two years ago, this research's results follow both the trade-off and stakeholders' theories; as for the trade-off theory, fulfilling ESG responsibility can negatively impact financial stability in the short run. Hence, whenever a company gets more involved in ESG, the corresponding costs tend to rise, and profits tend to fall, thus generating a loss in terms of shareholder value, this is called the substitution effect [12], this negative impact will gradually weaken. Since that, the Stakeholder's theory is valid in explaining how creating long-term relationship with stakeholders will maximize firm's profits and maximize shareholders' wealth which will maximize the firm's stability in consequence in the long-term [7,8]. From a long-term perspective, fulfilling ESG can help promote the relationship between the management and various stakeholders, thus improve firm stability. Specifically, by satisfying the various stakeholders' needs, a firm can establish a reputation and establish competitive advantages [9,10]. Therefore, the promotion effect based on the stakeholder theory may need to be manifested in the long term. This means that effective ESG practices can create negative results in the context of corporate financial stability in the short-term, while these negative results will gradually weaken and turn to be positive in the long-term. This research confirms both theories in the context of the Egyptian market. Hence, firms should focus on increasing the firm's value by having high costs at the short-term, but this will be compensated in the long-term by satisfied stakeholders and by consequence a higher/better firm's value. Also, it can't be ignored that the

Egyptian government is only applying the decree's first stage (compliance stage) and it is in process of applying the decree's second stage (the stage of exposure to legal accountability and the application of fines or penalties on non-compliant companies).

As the FRA's decree no. 108/2021 is applied in two stages: the first stage: the compliance or explain stage and the second stage: the stage of exposure to legal accountability and the application of fines or penalties on non-compliant companies. It is suggested that further research examine a comparative study of the effects of ESG disclosure for the first stage (the compliance or explain stage) and the second stage (the stage of exposure to legal accountability and the application of fines or penalties on non-compliant companies) of the decree, for EGX listed firms, which will provide productive and fruitful comparisons. Further, it would be interesting to examine the moderating role of some other factors on the relationship between ESG and firms' stability, such as: the CEO-duality, ownership concentration, foreign ownership and government ownership of firms.

6. Conclusions

To conclude, this study examined the relationships between the ESG and its individual dimensions (E, S and G) and financial stability (Z-score) among a sample of 106 listed firms in Egypt from 2020 to 2023 as an application of the FRA's decree no. 108/2021. At the aggregate level, the results indicated a negative significant relationship for the financial stability (Z-score). For the disaggregate level of ESG pillars (E, S and G), the results revealed that there was a significant negative relationship is found for E score and G score and the financial stability variable, measured by Z-score, while there is an insignificant negative for S score and Z-score. In general, the impact of fulfilling ESG responsibility on firm's financial stability can be viewed differently in the short run and the long run. Based on the "trade-off theory", fulfilling ESG responsibilities could negatively impact financial stability in the short run; costs tend to increase with the investment in ESG. The costs could be direct and indirect, such as: the costs associated with the treatment of waste, the expenses in planning, budgeting, managing and evaluating ESG. The indirect costs could be higher than documented since: waste management, investments in occupational health and safety, fair trade, expenses in employee welfare and community services and donations are all viewed as a firm's social responsibilities. Hence, whenever a company gets more involved in ESG, the corresponding costs tend to rise, and profits tend to fall, thus generating a loss in terms of shareholder value. Therefore, due to

the increased costs, fulfilling ESG responsibility may have a negative impact on financial stability; this is called the substitution effect, this negative impact will gradually weaken. Since that, the Stakeholder's theory is valid in explaining how creating long-term relationship with stakeholders will maximize firm's profits and maximize shareholders' wealth which will maximize the firm's stability in consequence in the long-term. This means that effective ESG practices can create negative results in the context of corporate financial stability in the short-term, while these negative results will gradually weaken and turn to be positive in the long-term. This research confirms both theories in the context of the Egyptian market.

As the FRA's decree no. 108/2021 is newly issued (only 3 years ago) and is applied in two stages: the first stage: the compliance or explain stage and the second stage: the stage of exposure to legal accountability and the application of fines or penalties on non-compliant companies. Till now only the first stage (the compliance or explain stage) is applied, in which companies comply with the model; where companies are committed to undertake annual ESG report prepared by their board of directors and attached to the annual financial statements, with the submission of a quarterly statement of the measures taken by the company regarding the aforementioned disclosures starting from January 2022. While, the second stage (the stage of exposure to legal accountability and the application of fines or penalties on non-compliant companies) is not yet implemented, but a reminder and warning email has already been sent by the Sustainable Development Department (SDD) of the Financial Regulatory Authority to the compliance officers of the companies entrusted with this decision.

Despite the findings reached, there are some limitations in this study that might be addressed in future research as follows: (1) The empirical analysis is based on a limited number of observations, (2) it covers the period between 2020–2023 which is not a large period due to the implication of the decree only for 2 years till now. Furthermore, for future research, it is recommended to carry out an event study that considers the decree's No. 108 of 2021 of ESG disclosure on larger period. Additionally, future research would benefit from variables more related to the Egyptian context, such as the CEO-duality, ownership concentration, foreign ownership and government ownership of firms.

Abbreviations

CG: Corporate Governance

CSR: Corporate Social Responsibility

E/ENV: Environmental

EBIT: Earnings Before Interest and Tax

EGX: Egyptian Stock Exchange

ESG: Environmental, Social and Governance

ESGD; Environmental, Social and Governance Disclosure

FRA: Financial Regulatory Authority

FS: Financial Stability

G/GOV: Governance

IR: Investor relations

KOSPI: Korea Composite Stock Price Index NBF: Non-Bank Financial Intermediaries

S/SOC: Social

SDD: Sustainable Development Department

SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals

UN: United Nations

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Data Availability Statement

The data is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Research Field

Ahmed Sakr: Corporate Finance, Accounting, Investments and Portfolio Management, Banking.

Mrwan Amer: Corporate Finance, Corporate Governance, Investment, Accounting.

Sara Wahid: Corporate Finance, Behavioral finance, Investment, Auditing.

Yasmine AbdelSalam: Corporate Finance, Corporate Governance, Accounting, Stock Market.